

Payment Innovation System and Financial Performance of Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

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Abstract

Existing literature indicate conflicting relationships between banks innovativeness and banks' profitability, while other researches merely report on bank payment innovations without relating the effectiveness of the purported innovations on bank profitability. Therefore, lack of adequate empirical evidence on the relationship between emerging banks' innovativeness and bank profitability motivated this study to examine the influence of payment innovations on profitability of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study was guided by Schumpeter theory of innovation. This research adopted explanatory survey research design. This study targeted managers from listed commercial banks headquarters in Nairobi city county, Kenya. The study sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's proportional sampling technique formula, which was drawn randomly from managers of commercial banks in Nairobi, Kenya. Primary data was collected by means of self-administered questionnaires. Data collected from the field was coded, cleaned, tabulated and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of specialized Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software and presented using tables to make them reader friendly. Descriptive statistics were used. Data was organized into graphs and tables for easy reference. Further, inferential statistics such as regression and correlation analyses was computed to determine both the nature and the strength of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Both descriptive and inferential statistics showed that the study's independent variable (payment innovations) significantly influenced financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study concluded that commercial banks that effectively utilize payment innovations system attract huge customer's base, save on transaction costs, thus boost bank's financial performance. The study recommends that one, commercial banks should roll out feasible payment innovations products and services to win customer trust and boost their financial performance.

Keywords: Financial Performance, Commercial Banks

Background of the Study

Turbulent financial performance of many financial lending institutions has attracted a myriad of researches on the most effective ways of mitigating financial loss, thus, the need for innovations. In this regard, Rosenbusch, Brinckmann and Bausch's (2011) meta-analysis of previous research on the relationship between innovation and firm performance aimed at establishing the direction and strength the relationship. Globally, in order to minimize costs, attract a larger market share and boost bank profitability in Brazil, private and state owned banks delivered financial services through retail agents including small supermarkets and pharmacies, post offices, and lottery kiosks. These agents are called banking correspondents (Kumar et al., 2006).

In January 2006, India's central bank issued a circular permitting banks to use post offices and specializes micro finance institutions, including nonprofit organizations cooperatives, and for profit companies as retail agents. The circular calls these agents business correspondents. In South Africa, branchless banking through retail agents is permitted only for licensed financial institutions (Harper et al., 2016).

Chinese commercial banks' traditional businesses operations mode 'the wholesale credit operations' have been changing and the ratio of commercial banks' retail businesses have been increasing. The financial performances of commercial banks in Kenya have been in a generally turbulent financial trend and these have mainly been

attributed to financial management issues and stiff competition from Micro finance institutions (CBK Annual Report, 2018). Statistics provide evidence of high concentration in the banking sector, which is likely to reduce small banks to mere followers and imitators of the financial innovations developed by large banks.

Statement of the Problem.

Banks innovativeness is meant to boost profitability but evidence from existing literature indicate conflicting relationships between banks innovativeness and banks' profitability, while other researches merely report on bank innovations without relating the effectiveness of the purported innovations on bank profitability (Cheng *et al.*, 2017).

For instance, in Kenya, Central Bank of Kenya (2017) indicated that, the number of automated teller machines grew from 166 in 2001 to 2091 in 2010, debit cards increased from 160,000 in 2001 to over 6 million cards in subsequent years while mobile banking transactions increased from 48,000 per annum in 2007 to over 450,000 transactions per annum in 2017..

More so, some researchers have revealed conflicting results on the relationship between payment innovations and financial performance. For instance Gopalakrishnan (2013) study found a reverse causality between payment innovation and bank financial performance and recommended further researches. World Bank (2016) study reported that there was an opportunity for up to 344 million people in developing economies to participate in debt crowd funding, as a form of digital credit, but few banks are aware of the innovation.

Therefore, lack of adequate empirical evidence on the relationship between banks innovativeness and bank profitability motivated this study to examine the influence of payment innovations on profitability of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Objectives of the Study.

To examine influence of payment innovation system on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Research Hypothesis

H₀₁: Payment innovation system does not significantly influence financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Significance of the Study.

Investors in the banking sector viable financial innovations that can minimize operational costs, attract and retain a large customer base and consequently boost bank profitability in terms of return on assets, return on investment and overall economic value. The study provided empirical evidence to financial researchers and scholars in understanding current trends in financial innovation in the banking industry, and their significant prediction on commercial banks profitability.

Scope of Study.

The study was only done on 12 listed commercial banks whose headquarters is in Nairobi County, and focused only on the influence of payment innovations predicting banking on financial performance of the 12 listed commercial banks. The study was done in June, 2020.

Limitation of Study.

Though respondents were unwilling to provide information for fear of exposing information that could be de-marketing the institution. This was overcome by assurance that this study ensure confidentiality and that the study is purely for academic purposes. Further, they were not supposed to write their names on the questionnaire

LITERATURE REVIEW**Theoretical review****Schumpeter theory of innovation**

Proposed by Schumpeter (1928), the theorist argued that entrepreneurs, who could be independent inventors or research and development engineers in large corporations, created the opportunity for new profits with their innovations. In turn, groups of imitators attracted by super-profits would start a wave of investment that would erode the profit margin for the innovation. However, before the economy could equilibrate a new innovation or set of innovations, conceptualized by Schumpeter as Kondratiev cycles, would emerge to begin the business cycle over again.

That is, according to Freeman, (1994), Schumpeter saw innovations as perpetual gales of creative destruction that were essential forces driving growth rates in a capitalist system. Schumpeter's thinking evolved over his lifetime to the extent that some scholars have differentiated his early thinking where innovation was largely dependent on exceptional individuals/entrepreneurs willing to take on exceptional hazards as an act of will. His later thinking recognized the role of large corporations in organizing and supporting innovation. This resulted in his emphasis on the role of oligopolies in innovation and which later was falsely viewed as the main contribution of his work.

In relation to the banking industry, Schumpeter drew a clear distinction between the entrepreneurs whose innovations create the conditions for profitable new enterprises and the bankers who create credit to finance the construction of the new ventures (Schumpeter, 1939). He emphasized that the special role of credit-creation by bankers was 'the monetary complement of innovations' (Schumpeter, 1939). As independent agents who have no proprietary interest in the new enterprises they finance, bankers are the capitalists who bear all the risks (none is borne by the entrepreneurs). That requires having the special ability to judge the potential for success in financing entrepreneurial activities. Schumpeter emphasized that it is just as important to deny credit to those lacking that potential as it is to supply credit to those having it (Schumpeter, 1939).

Therefore, Schumpeter theory of innovation is relevant to this study in the sense that banking innovations emerge as advanced entrepreneurial skills meant to make commercial banks maintain a competitive financial edge against rivals and also for the very reason of remaining relevant in the current turbulent competitive business environment in Kenya.

Independent Variables**Dependent Variable**

Bank Innovative Systems

Commercial Banks Financial Performance

Payment innovation system

- E-Bill payments
- E-Fund transfers
- Retail Payment Services

Return on Assets**Figure 2.3: Conceptual Framework.****Review of study variables****Payment innovations and bank financial performance**

This assessed the influence of payment innovations such as electronic billing, electronic funds transfers and electronic card payments on profitability of commercial banks. For instance, Cheng et al., (2017) study on payment innovations found that electronic payment services are provided on an electronic billing platform connected to the bank payment and settlement systems of e-commerce companies and commercial banks.

That is, electronic payment innovation rose as a way to resolve problems of trust and financial transaction security between buyers and sellers. Thus, it is able to effectively promote the convenience and applicability of traditional cash payments, money transfers, and bank card payments by utilizing innovative payment technology supported by the internet, thus minimizing manual transactions (Cheng et al., 2017).

Empirical review of literature related to the study**Payment innovations and financial performance of banks**

Cheng *et al.* (2017) study on payment innovations found that electronic payment services are provided on an electronic billing platform connected to the bank payment and settlement systems of e-commerce companies and commercial banks. That is, this rose as a way to resolve problems of trust and financial transaction security between buyers and sellers. Thus, it is able to effectively promote the convenience and applicability of traditional cash payments, money transfers, and bank card payments by utilizing innovative payment technology supported by the internet, thus minimizing manual transactions.

Further, DeYoung, Lang and Nolle's (2014) study of 424 community banks comprising the earliest adopters of payment innovations using internet banking in USA explains the implication of financial innovation adoption. The study compares the change in the banks' 1999 – 2001 financial performance with that of 5175 community banks using branch-only banking. They found an improvement in the profitability of the early adopters of electronic payments using internet banking among community banks associated with internet banking.

In addition, Hernando and Nieto (2015) study provided a quantitative analysis of the impact of electronic payment innovations and the financial performance of 72 banks in Spain. They found that the reduction in transaction costs due to electronic payments leads to an expansion in the banks' profitability.

Gopalakrishnan (2013) study however found a reverse causality between payment innovation and financial performance. That is, a reverse or circular relationship between payment innovation and firm performance is evidenced by the higher propensity for better performing firms to innovate and commit their capital to innovation. The relationship between payment innovation and firm performance is therefore two-way, meaning there is a reverse causation between the two. For instance; firms with high turnover, as evidenced by high sales growth shows above-average innovation expenditure in information communication technology in both hardware and software.

Iftekhhar, Schmiedel and Song (2009) study found that retail payment transaction technologies have an intensifying effect on the relationship between retail payment services and bank performance. That is advanced retail payment transaction technologies fosters innovation and growth in the retail banking sector. This further creates more value associated with retail payment services for banks. On the other hand, if more retail payment transactions have been done through ATMs or POS instead of retail payments offices, banks can be more cost efficient and obtain more income. The study concluded that Innovations of retail payment services have a larger impact on bank performance in countries with a relatively high adoption of retail payment transaction technologies.

Further, ATMs as studied by Massoud and Bernhardt (2002) consider the possibility that ATM surcharges can impact banks profitability, both directly as well as indirectly through a so-called customer relationship effect. This indirect effect results from a customer at a small bank with relatively few ATMs switching his/her deposit account to a larger bank with a larger number of ATMs in order to avoid paying ATM surcharges. If switching occurs then higher ATM surcharges should result in an increase in the market share of bank products (e.g. deposits) and profitability of larger banks and a decrease in the market share of deposits and profitability of smaller banks.

Aduda and Kingoo's (2012) study on the relationship between electronic banking and financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya finds a strong positive relationship between bank performance and e-payment innovations. Using ROA as proxy for bank performance and the number of ATMs and debit cards as proxy for e-banking, Further, Aduda and Kingoo (2012) found that payment innovations contributes to performance of large firms as well as small and medium enterprises.

Knowledge Gap

Evidence from the literature indicates that most of the studies on innovation and firm performance have been carried out in developed countries. However, critical success factors for innovation may not be replicable across geographical regions and markets due to cultural differences, but this cannot completely hinder their application (Al-Ansari, Pervan & Xu 2013). Therefore lack of adequate empirical evidence on the significant role of emerging banking innovations in commercial banks motivated this study to examine the influence of payment innovations on financial performance of listed Commercial banks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed explanatory survey research design. This is because it is suitable for exploring relationships and describes behavior or reactions of people to a given phenomenon in the society (Hair *et al.*, 2006). It examined an association between the conceptualized independent and dependent variables as shown in the study's conceptual model.

Population of the Study.

This study targeted managers from 12 listed commercial banks headquarters in Nairobi city County, Kenya, stratified as shown in table 3.1; target population.

Table 3. 1: Target population

Category of employee	No. of targeted respondents
Internal audit managers	12
Risk Managers	12
Compliance Managers	12
ICT managers	12
Loans managers	12
Personal banking managers	12
Finance managers	12
Debt Collection Managers	12
Credit Managers	12
Human Resource Managers	12
Total	120

Sampling Frame

A sampling frame is a list of all the items in the population (Cooper & Schinder, (2007). It is a complete list of everyone or everything you want to study or a list of things that you draw a sample from. In this study it consisted of senior managers of all listed commercial banks whose headquarters is in Nairobi city County, Kenya.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

Sample Size

In this study, the study sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's proportional sampling technique formula. The importance of this expression is that it gives a researcher the required sampling interval for a given population and a known sample. Therefore a sample size has been calculated as per Taro Yamane's proportional sampling technique formula shown as follows;

Sample

$$n = N / (1 + (e)^2)$$

Where n = Sample size

N = population under study

E = margin error (0.05)

I = constant

Therefore;

$$n = 120 / (1 + 120 (0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 120 / (1 + 120(0.0025))$$

$$n = 120 / (1 + 0.3); n = 120 / 1.3$$

$$n = 92$$

From the calculation 92 and were drawn randomly from managers of commercial banks headquarters in Nairobi city county, Kenya as per the break down in table 3.2.

Table 3. 2: Sample Size

Category of Staff	No. of Senior Management Staff (N)	Sample n= (N/Target Pop.) x Sample size
Internal audit managers	12	10
Risk Managers	12	10
Compliance Managers	12	9
ICT managers	12	9
Loans managers	12	9
Personal banking managers	12	9
Finance managers	12	9
Debt Collection Mangers	12	9
Credit Managers	12	9
Human Resource Managers	12	9
Total	120	92

Sampling techniques

The study employed stratified random sampling technique which guided how sampled managers of commercial banks headquarters in Nairobi city county, Kenya, are to be selected. This eliminated biasness.

Data collection Instruments

Primary data was collected by means of self-administered questionnaires. These questionnaires were structured and designed in multiple choice formats. Section one introduced the researcher, topic of research and its purpose to the respondent. Section two was designed to elicit demographic data of the respondents such as gender, level of education and age while section three dwelled on independent and dependent variable of the study.

Data collection procedure

Researcher secured legitimate documents such as researcher's introductory letter, respondents' consent forms and a letter of identification. The questionnaires were self-administered through sending hard copies of the questionnaires to the respondents and picking them when dully filled. In the process, the respondents were assured of confidentiality in that the information obtained was for the purpose of the study only.

Data Processing and analysis

Data collected from the field was coded, cleaned, tabulated and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of specialized Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).version 24 software. The output of analysis was presented using tables to make them reader friendly.

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages as well as measures of central tendency (means) and dispersion (standard deviation) was used. Data was also organized into graphs and tables for easy reference.

Further, inferential statistics such as regression and correlation analyses was used to determine both the nature and the strength of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Correlation analysis is usually used together with regression analysis to measure how well the regression line explains the variation of the dependent variable. The linear and multiple regression plus correlation analyses were based on the association between two (or more) variables. SPSS version 24 is the analysis computer software that was used to compute statistical data.

Study conceptualized Regression Model;

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e$$

y = financial performance of commercial banks in Nairobi city County

β_0 = Constant

X_1 = payment innovations

$\{\beta_0 - \beta_4\}$ = Beta coefficients

e = the error term

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.2 Response Rate.

From 92 questionnaires that were dispatched for data collection, 77 questionnaires were returned completely filled, representing a response rate of 83.6% which is good for generalizability of the research findings to a wider population. The high response rate was achieved because the researcher patiently waited for respondents to completely fill the questionnaire before picking them.

Reliability and Validity of Research Instruments

Validity of research instruments was checked using content validity where all questions were checked for clarity of words and ensuring all questions had adequate content as per the study variables. Reliability of research instruments was tested using Cronbach alpha; which tests internal consistency and the results in table 4.1 shows Cronbach alpha coefficients values of 0.7 and above confirming that reliability of the study's research instruments.

Table 4. 1: Results of Reliability test

Variable	Number of items	Cronbach alpha
Payment innovations	6	.809
Financial performance	6	.815

4.4.2 Descriptive statistics: Payment innovation and banks' financial performance

These are summarized responses on whether payment innovations influence financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The descriptive results are presented in table 4.4.

Table 4. 2: Descriptive statistics; Payment innovation system

Statement	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std Dev
1.The bank has varied electronic payment services to its customers	14(18.2)	36(46.7)	9(11.7)	11(14.3)	7(9.1)	3.51	0.931
2.The bank has realized an increase in financial performance after adoption of an effective electronic funds transfer system	13(16.8)	32(41.6)	12(15.6)	9(11.7)	11(14.3)	3.36	0.934
3.The electronic billing system really saves on banks transaction costs	11(14.3)	39(50.6)	7(9.1)	10(13.0)	10(13.0)	3.49	0.923
4.Adoption of an effective electronic bank card payments saves on banks transaction costs and improve bank financial performance	12(15.5)	37(48.1)	11(14.3)	8(10.4)	9(11.7)	3.45	0.912
5.The bank adopted electronic payments to resolve problems of trust and financial transaction security with its customers	15(19.5)	31(40.2)	9(11.7)	10(13.0)	12(15.6)	3.39	0.929
6.Generally, secure and upgraded electronic payment systems save on transaction costs and boost bank financial performance	14(18.2)	36(46.8)	10(13.0)	9(11.7)	8(10.3)	3.55	0.942
Valid list wise=77							
Grand mean =3.46							

From table 4.4, most respondents agreed (46.7%) and strongly agreed (18.2%) that the bank has varied electronic payment services to its customers; which also supported by 41.6% of respondents who agreed that the bank has realized an increase in financial performance after adoption of an effective electronic funds transfer system; implying that banks' electronic payment services to its customers has made banks realize a significant growth in financial performance.

More so, 50.6% of respondents agreed that the electronic billing system really saves on banks transaction costs; while 48.1% of respondents also agreed that adoption of an effective electronic bank card payments saves on banks transaction costs and improve bank financial performance; meaning that introduction of electronic billing system and effective electronic bank card payments saves banking transaction costs and boost the banks' financial performance.

Further, 40.2% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed (19.5%) that the bank adopted electronic payments to resolve problems of trust and financial transaction security with its customers; implying that customers that have embraced electronic payment system makes the banks save on manual payment transactions, thus, boost banks' financial performance.

Lastly, most respondents agreed (46.8%) and strongly agreed (18.2%) (supported by the grand mean = 3.46= 4 = agree) that generally, secure and upgraded electronic payment systems save on transaction costs and boost bank financial performance. This is supported by Cheng et al., (2017) assertion that electronic payment innovation rose as a way to resolve problems of trust and financial transaction security between buyers and sellers. Thus, it is able to effectively promote the convenience and applicability of traditional cash payments, money transfers, and bank card payments by utilizing innovative payment technology supported by the internet, thus minimizing manual transactions.

Linear regression results

This tested the linear influence of Payment innovations on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. This was computed by SPSS based on transformed data from categorical data to continuous data so as to run regression analyses based on continuous data.

Linear influence of payment innovation on financial performance

This tested the direct influence of payment innovation on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The results are shown table 4.9.

Table 4. 3: Direct influence of payment innovations on financial performance

Model Summary										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.753 ^a	.568	.562	.80708	.568	98.422	1	75	.000	
ANOVA ^b										
Model	Sum of Squares		Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.				
1	Regression	64.110	1	64.110	98.422	.000 ^a				
	Residual	48.854	75	.651						
	Total	112.964	76							
Coefficients ^a										
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.			
		B	Std. Error	Beta						
1	(Constant)	.921	.269		3.422	.001				
	Payment innovations	.801	.081	.753	9.921	.000				

a. Dependent Variable: Financial performance

From table 4.9, the model summary shows that $R^2 = 0.568$; implying that 56.8% variations in the financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya is explained by payment innovation while other factors not in the study model accounts for 43.2% of variation in financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. Further, coefficient analysis shows that payment innovation has positive significant influence on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta = 0.801$ (0.081); at $p < .01$). This implies that a single improvement in effective payment innovations will lead to 0.801 unit increase in the financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. Therefore, the linear regression equation is;

$$(ii) y = 0.921 + 0.801X_1$$

Where;

y = financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

X_1 = payment innovation

Multiple regression analysis

Multiple regression analysis was computed to assess the multivariate influence of the study's independent variables (payment innovations) on the dependent variable (financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya). This was after the compulsory assumptions of multiple regression analyses were checked and met. The multiple regression results are shown in table 4.12.

Table 4. 4: Multiple regression results

Model Summary										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.851 ^a	.724	.708	.65825	.724	47.177	4	72	.000	
ANOVA ^b										
Model	Sum of Squares		Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.				

1	Regression	81.767	4	20.442	47.177	.000 ^a
	Residual	31.197	72	.433		
	Total	112.964	76			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Payment innovations.

b. Dependent Variable: Financial performance

Multiple regression analysis in table 4.12 shows the multiple regression results of the combined influence of the study's independent variable (payment innovations). The model's R squared (R^2) is 0.724 which shows that the study explains 72.4% of variation in the financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya, while other factors not in the conceptualized study model accounts for 27.6 %, hence, it is a good study model.

Furthermore, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) shows the mean squares and F statistics significant ($F = 47.177$; significant at $p < .001$), thus confirming the fitness of the model and also implies that the study's independent variable (payment innovations) has significant variations in their contributions to financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Finally, the values of unstandardized regression coefficients with standard errors in parenthesis in table 4.13 indicate that all the study's independent variable (payment innovations; $\beta = 0.613$ (0.151) at $p < 0.05$ significantly influenced financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya (dependent variable).

In this regard, the study's final multiple regression equation is;

$$(v) y = 0.610 + 0.613X_1$$

Where;

y= financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya

X_1 = payment innovations

Table 4. 5: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.610	.151		4.035	.000
Payment innovations	.613	.151	.550	4.070	.000
AI predictive banking	.426	.138	.400	3.080	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Financial performance

Testing of study hypotheses

Study hypothesis (H_{01}) stated that payment innovation system does not significantly influence financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. Multiple regression results indicate that payment innovation system significantly influence financial performance of listed commercial banks ($\beta = 0.466$ (0.106) at $p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis is therefore rejected. The results indicate that that a single improvement in effective payment innovations will lead to 0.466 unit increase in the financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

The results are supported by DeYoung, Lang and Nolle's (2014) study of 424 community banks comprising the earliest adopters of payment innovations using internet banking in USA explains the implication of financial innovation adoption. The study compares the change in the banks' 1999 – 2001 financial performance with that of 5175 community banks using branch-only banking. They found an improvement in the profitability of the early adopters of electronic payments using internet banking among community banks associated with internet banking.

Gopalakrishnan (2013) study however found a reverse causality between payment innovation and financial performance. That is, a reverse or circular relationship between payment innovation and firm performance is evidenced by the higher propensity for better performing firms to innovate and commit their capital to

innovation. The relationship between payment innovation and firm performance is therefore two-way, meaning there is a reverse causation between the two. For instance; firms with high turnover, as evidenced by high sales growth shows above-average innovation expenditure in information communication technology in both hardware and software.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary of the Study.

This tested the influence of payment innovation system on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study found that payment innovation systems such as E-Bill payments, E-Fund transfers, Retail payment services significantly influenced financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

The study results support earlier researches that found that an improvement in the profitability of the early adopters of electronic payments innovations using internet banking. However, other researchers found a reverse causality between payment innovations and financial performance. That is, a reverse or circular relationship between payment innovation and firm performance was evidenced by the higher propensity for better performing banks to innovate and commit their capital to innovation as compared to smaller banks.

Conclusion.

Based on the above findings, the study concludes that commercial banks that efficiently adopt cost effective electronic payment innovations can enhance their financial performance

Recommendation

The study recommends that innovators in commercial banks should adopt secure and cost effective payment innovations systems that can attract and retain a huge customer base.

Areas for Further Study.

First, a similar study can be done on all commercial banks in Kenya using time series analysis so as to compare study findings. Secondly, a similar study can be done on Micro Finance Banking institutions so as to assess the effectiveness of the adopted banking innovations.

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